

A 0.3% measurement of **orbital decay**
in the 12.75-min WD+WD **J0651+2844**

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A **syzygy** (from the Ancient Greek σύζυγος, 'yoked together') is a (roughly) straight-line configuration of three or more celestial bodies.

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J0651+2844: The 12.75-min WD+WD Binary

Average distance between the Earth and the Moon: 384,400 km

J0651+2844: The 12.75-min WD+WD Binary

“We discovered that J0651 is a compact binary system when **back-to-back spectra** separated by six minutes showed a ≈ 1300 km/s change in radial velocity.”

*Brown et al. 2011,
ApJ, 737, L23*

J0651+2844: The 12.75-min WD+WD Binary

phase = 0

- Eclipses detected on 01 April 2011 from the 2.1m at McDonald Observatory

*Brown et al. 2011,
ApJ, 737, L23*

Eclipses were detected on **1 April 2011** from the 2.1m telescope at McDonald Observatory on the first night of a 14-night run

John Kuehne

The Rock House fire
started on **9 April 2011**
near Marfa, TX

It eventually burned
>310,000 acres
(>1270 km²)

Photos I took on 9 April 2011

Photo by Don Winget on 11 April 2011

We re-started monitoring the 12.75-min binary on **13 April 2011**,
the first photons collected at McDonald after the Rock House fire started.

Photo by Frank Cianciolo on 17 April 2011

Within 13 Months We Confirmed Orbital Decay

In 2012:

$$dP_{\text{orb}}/dt = (-0.31 \pm 0.09) \text{ ms/yr}$$

O-C Diagrams Measure Tiny Period Changes

Imagine a **leaky faucet**, dripping exactly every **12 min**, but sediment buildup is **slowing the drip by 0.5 ms every year**:

**Drip 1: 1 January 2014,
at UT 00:00:00**

O-C Diagrams Measure Tiny Period Changes

Imagine a **leaky faucet**, dripping exactly every **12 min**, but sediment buildup is **slowing the drip by 0.5 ms every year**:

Updated Spectroscopy of J0651+2844

J0651+2844 is a
single-lined binary

6.5m MMT

10m Keck

$T_{\text{eff},1} = 16,700 \pm 200 \text{ K}$
 $M_1 = 0.261 \pm 0.010 M_{\odot}$
 $K_1 = 617.9 \pm 5.8 \text{ km s}^{-1}$
 $i = 86.3 \pm 1.0 \text{ deg}$
 $T_{\text{eff},2} = 10,370 \pm 360 \text{ K}$
 $M_2 = 0.509 \pm 0.029 M_{\odot}$

A Search for Primary Rotation in J0651+2844

We do not detect the Rossiter-McLaughlin effect around primary eclipses:

$$P_{\text{spin},1} > 6.7 \text{ min}$$

10m Keck

Updated Light Curve Modeling of J0651+2844

$$R_1 = 0.03596$$
$$\pm 0.00091 R_\odot$$

(implies $M_1 =$
 $0.252 \pm 0.010 M_\odot$
in line with
 $0.261 M_\odot$ from
surface gravity)

$$R_2 = 0.01319$$
$$\pm 0.00033 R_\odot$$

$$i = 86.3 \pm 1.0 \text{ deg}$$

$$d_{\text{LC}} = 1050 \pm 120 \text{ pc}$$

$$d_{\text{Gaia}} = 1080^{+930}_{-400} \text{ pc}$$

We **expect** $dP_{\text{orb}}/dt = (-0.263 \pm 0.020) \text{ ms/yr}$ from GR (point masses) and
observe $(-0.28688 \pm 0.00072) \text{ ms/yr}$!
 – a 0.3% measurement!

We **expect** $dP_{\text{orb}}/dt = (-0.263 \pm 0.020) \text{ ms/yr}$ from GR (point masses) and
observe $(-0.2879 \pm 0.0022) \text{ ms/yr}$!
 using a sine fit to half the orbital period (ellipsoidal variations)

Tides expected to
 increase dP_{orb}/dt by $\approx 5\%$

*see Piro 2011, Benaquista 2011,
 Burkart et al. 2013, Fuller & Lai
 2013, Dall'Osso & Rossi 2014*

$$M_{\text{tot}} = 0.770 \pm 0.039 M_{\odot}$$

$$L_{\text{GW}} = 2.85 L_{\odot}$$

$$L_{\text{EM}} = 0.05 L_{\odot}$$

*Hermes et al. 2019,
 (nearly) submitted*

Tidal bulge is aligned with
syzygy to at least 0.4 s
(0.05% of orbit)

J0651+2844: The 12.75-min WD+WD Binary

- 8 years since discovery: $dP_{\text{orb}}/dt = (-0.28688 \pm 0.00072) \text{ ms/y}$
 - The GW luminosity exceeds the EM luminosity by factor of $>50!$
- This is 1.2σ consistent with pure GR: $(-0.263 \pm 0.020) \text{ ms/yr}$
 - This uncertainty is dominated by the uncertainty in M_2
- $f_{\text{orb}} = 2.6136734171(89) \text{ mHz}$, an exceptional *LISA* verification!
- We will know dP_{orb}/dt to 0.1% by 2021

